

Triterpenoid Glycosides from Fruits of *Ecballium elaterium*[‡]

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Methanol extract of fresh fruits of *Ecballium elaterium* A. Rich yielded five triterpenoid glycosides which were characterized as oleanolic acid 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (1), 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3 β -hydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid 28-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (2), oleanolic acid 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 2)- β -D-glucopyranoside (3), 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3 β -hydroxy-11-oxo-olean-12-en-28-oic acid 28-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (4), and oleanolic acid 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 3)[β -D-glucopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 2)]- β -D-glucopyranoside (5). The last two compounds found to be new were designated as elateroside A and B respectively. Structures of the compounds were elucidated by 2D-nmr and other spectral analyses.

The fruits of *Ecballium elaterium* A. Rich (Cucurbitaceae) are used as a delicious vegetable in India, particularly in the eastern part of the country. In the Indian system of medicine, the fruits are used as a powerful hydragogue cathartic¹. Recently, the plant has also been reported to possess antitumor activity². A number of sterols and cucurbitacins have so far been reported from this plant³⁻⁵. However, during chemical investigation in our laboratory on the fresh unripe mature fruits, the presence of cucurbitacins could not be detected. On the contrary, five triterpenoid glycosides (1-5) were isolated from the methanol extract of the fruits. We report herein the isolation and structure elucidation of the compounds.

- 1 R = glc —, R' = H, R'' = H₂
 - 2 R = glc —, R' = glc —, R'' = H₂
 - 3 R = glc —, 2 glc —, R' = H, R'' = H₂
 - 4 R = glc —, R' = glc —, R'' = O
 - 5 R = gal —, 3 glc —, R' = H, R'' = H₂
- |
2
|
glc

Results and Discussion

The methanol extract of the fresh fruits of *E. elaterium* A. Rich was successively extracted with petroleum ether and chloroform. Column chromatography of the chloroform extract over silica gel followed by prep.-HPLC yielded five pure triterpenoid glycosides (1-5).

Compound 1, m.p. 235–36°, [α]_D + 54.3°, on hydroly-

sis with 1*N* HCl yielded oleanolic acid and D-glucose. The compound was identified as oleanolic acid 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside⁶ by detailed analysis of its 2D-nmr spectra, particularly the HMBC spectrum which also resulted in the unambiguous assignment of the ¹³C and ¹H chemical shifts of the compound (Tables 1 and 2).

Compound 2, m.p. 168–70°, [α]_D+18.5°, showed the signals for 42 carbons in its ¹³C nmr spectrum. Of these, 30 signals were assigned to the aglycone moiety and 12 signals including two anomeric carbon signals to the two sugar units. A comparison of the ¹³C chemical shifts of the compound with those of 1 (Table 1) revealed that the resonance frequencies of the carbons of the aglycone moiety and one sugar unit were very close to those of 1 except that of C-28 (δ 176.46) which experienced up-field shift by ~4 ppm indicating that in 2, one more sugar unit is attached to C-28 of 1 through an ester linkage. This was indeed confirmed by its hydrolysis with 5% NaOH to 1 and D-glucose. The β -linkage of both the glucose units with the aglycone was evident from the coupling constant of 7.9 Hz of the two anomeric proton doublets at δ 4.951 and 5.446 in its ¹H nmr spectrum (Table 2). The compound was, therefore, identified as 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3 β -hydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid 28-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside⁷.

Compound 3, m.p. 201–02°, [α]_D+28.5°, showed in its negative ion FAB-MS, the [M-H]⁻ at *m/z* 779 corresponding to the molecular formula C₄₂H₆₈O₁₃. Its ¹³C nmr spectrum (Table 1) exhibited signals for 42 carbons, of which 30 carbons were assigned to the aglycone and 12 carbon signals to the sugar units. The chemical shifts of the carbons of the aglycone moiety were found to be very close to those of the aglycone moiety of oleanolic acid 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (1) (Table 1) whose structure was fully elucidated on the basis of HMBC and other 2D-nmr, viz. ¹H-¹H COSY, ¹H-¹³C COSY, HSQC and NOESY spectral analyses. It was, therefore, evident that 3 also contains ole-

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TABLE 1—¹³C CHEMICAL SHIFTS (125 MHz, δ, TMS) OF 1-5 IN PYRIDINE-d₅

Carbon	1	2	3	4	5
1	38.72	38.75	38.72	37.48	39.67
2	26.60	26.59	26.59	26.71	26.55
3	88.84	88.86	89.00	88.63	89.33
4	39.53	39.52	39.53	39.93	39.60
5	55.84	55.82	55.84	55.46	55.77
6	18.50	18.53	18.49	17.66	18.49
7	33.22*	33.15	33.22*	33.19	33.18*
8	39.76	39.93	39.74	44.00	39.72
9	48.02	48.03	48.01	62.17	47.97
10	37.02	36.99	36.96	37.48	36.95
11	23.79	23.80	23.80	199.96	23.79
12	122.53	122.88	122.47	128.33	122.51
13	144.89	144.19	144.89	168.79	144.90
14	42.19	42.15	42.18	46.51	42.16
15	28.34	30.02	28.35	28.19	28.33
16	23.72	22.97	23.74	23.17	23.72
17	46.69	47.01	46.73	45.57	46.69
18	42.02	41.77	42.05	42.14	42.03
19	46.51	46.23	46.57	44.32	46.52
20	31.00	30.79	30.99	30.69	30.99
21	34.26	34.02	34.28	33.77	34.25
22	33.29*	32.55	33.26*	31.58	33.24*
23	28.28	28.27	28.23	28.26	28.02
24	17.05	17.05	16.85	17.05	16.76
25	15.48	15.58	15.48	16.73	15.44
26	17.42	17.50	17.43	19.48	17.40
27	26.21	26.13	26.21	23.65	26.21
28	180.23	176.46	180.49	176.09	180.22
29	33.22	33.15	33.32	32.80	33.31
30	23.79	23.67	23.80	23.34	23.79
C(3)-Glucose (G)					
G-1	106.94	106.94	105.07	106.96	104.99
G-2	75.84	75.82	83.39	75.81	79.28
G-3	78.80	78.78	78.37	78.80	88.71
G-4	71.89	71.85	71.61	71.83	69.98
G-5	78.34	78.33	78.05	78.35	77.66
G-6	63.08	63.04	62.83	62.99	62.60
Glucose (G')					
G'-1	-	95.78	106.03	96.03	103.82
G'-2	-	74.16	77.15	74.21	76.43
G'-3	-	79.36	77.95	79.54	78.60
G'-4	-	71.11	71.66	71.09	72.58
G'-5	-	78.92	78.82	78.83	77.80
G'-6	-	62.22	62.71	62.26	63.40
Galactose (Gal)					
Gal-1	-	-	-	-	105.24
Gal-2	-	-	-	-	72.95
Gal-3	-	-	-	-	75.40
Gal-4	-	-	-	-	70.14
Gal-5	-	-	-	-	77.35
Gal-6	-	-	-	-	61.96

*Values in a vertical column may be interchanged.

 TABLE 2—¹H CHEMICAL SHIFTS* (500 MHz, δ, TMS) OF 3-5 IN PYRIDINE-d₅

¹ H	1	3	4	5
H ₃ -23	1.337	1.300	1.337	1.271
H ₃ -24	1.007	1.107	1.033	1.082
H ₃ -25	0.830	0.829	1.240	0.791
H ₃ -26	1.007	1.002	1.279	0.980
H ₃ -27	1.321	1.306	1.430	1.306
H ₃ -29	0.968	0.966	0.903	0.964
H ₃ -30	1.021	1.020	0.808	1.017
H _{ax} -3	3.411 dd (12.4, 4.0)	3.290 (over- lapped with H-18 signal)	3.439 dd (11.8, 4.4)	3.285 (over- lapped with H-18 signal)
H-12	5.494 dd (3.5, 3.5)	5.486 dd (3.2, 3.2)	5.961	5.477 dd (3.2, 3.2)
C(3) Glucose (G)				
G-1	4.964 d (8.0)	4.926 d (7.6)	4.956 d (7.9)	4.840 d (7.9)
G-2	4.063 t (8.2)	4.255 t (7.9)	-	4.36
G-3	4.284 t (8.8)	4.339 t (9.0)	-	4.25
G-4	4.252 t (8.8)	4.177 t (9.0)	-	4.04 t (9.0)
G-5	4.036 m	3.950 m	-	3.84 m
G-6	4.438 dd (11.6, 5.5), 4.612 dd (11.6, 2.5)	4.373 dd (11.6, 5.5), 4.565 dd (11.6, 2.1)	-	4.30
Glucose (G')				
G'-1	-	5.386 d (7.6)	6.329 d (8.3)	5.687 d (7.9)
G'-2	-	4.142 dd (7.6, 9.0)	-	4.10 t (8.5)
G'-3	-	4.261 t (9.0)	-	4.27
G'-4	-	4.358 t (9.0)	-	4.17
G'-5	-	3.922 m	-	3.84 m
G'-6	-	4.468 dd (11.6, 4.0) 4.507 dd (11.6, 3.4)	-	4.27 4.33
Galactose (Gal)				
Gal-1	-	-	-	5.297 d (7.6)
Gal-2	-	-	-	4.51
Gal-3	-	-	-	4.15
Gal-4	-	-	-	4.49
Gal-5	-	-	-	4.16
Gal-6	-	-	-	4.38 4.46

*The chemical shifts were assigned unambiguously on the basis of 2D-nmr, viz. ¹H-¹H COSY, ¹H-¹³C COSY, ¹H-¹H HOHAHA, HMBC and NOESY spectral analyses. Unless otherwise stated, the signals are singlets. Figures in the parentheses are the coupling constants in Hz. In case of 4, the protons of the sugar moieties could not be assigned due to poor spectral quality because of the paucity of material.

anolic acid as the aglycone as in 1. The remaining 12 carbon atoms, all resonating between δ 62.0 and 106.0 demonstrated the presence of two hexose units in the molecule. Both the hexose residues were identified as D-glucose by acid hydrolysis of 3 followed by HPTLC of the hydrolysate. The comparatively deshielded chemical shift of

C-3 of the aglycone (δ 89.00) and almost identical chemical shift of C-28 (δ 180.49) with that of 1 clearly indicated that a disaccharide moiety is linked to C-3 of the aglycone in this compound. That both the glucose units are β -linked was evident from the multiplicity and coupling constant of the anomeric proton signals at δ 4.926 and 5.386 as doublets with J 7.6 Hz. The ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum of the compound showed the following correlations :

- (i) δ 5.386 (G'-H-1) \leftrightarrow 4.142 (G'-H-2) \leftrightarrow 4.261 (G'-H-3)
- (ii) δ 4.358 (G'-H-4) \leftrightarrow 3.922 (G'-H-5) \leftrightarrow 4.468 and 4.507 (G'-H₂-6)
- (iii) δ 4.926 (G-H-1) \leftrightarrow 4.255 (G-H-2)
- (iv) δ 4.177 (G-H-4) \leftrightarrow 3.950 (G-H-5) \leftrightarrow 4.373 and 4.565 (G-H₂-6)

On the basis of the above ^1H chemical shift assignments (Table 2), ^{13}C chemical shifts could be unambiguously assigned to specific carbons of both the glucose units (Table 1) from its ^1H - ^{13}C COSY spectrum. The ^{13}C nmr data clearly demonstrated that the glucose units are coupled through 1 \rightarrow 2 linkage. The HMBC spectrum of the compound exhibited correlations between the anomeric proton signal (δ 5.386) of the terminal glucose with C-2 (δ 83.39) of the inner glucose, and the anomeric proton signal of the inner glucose (δ 4.926) with C-3 (δ 89.00) of the aglycone moiety. The above structural assignment was fully corroborated by the NOESY spectrum which showed NOE interactions as depicted in Fig. 1.

Based on the above evidence, compound 3 could be represented as oleanolic acid 3- O - β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- β -D-glucopyranoside⁸. It may be mentioned here that though the observed m.p. and $[\alpha]_D$ values of the compound were found to vary significantly (*vide* Experimental) from those reported⁸, the ^1H and ^{13}C nmr data were very close to the reported values.

Compound 4, designated a elateroside A, m.p. 158–60°, $[\alpha]_D +15.2^\circ$, showed in its negative ion FAB-MS, the $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$ at m/z 793 corresponding to the molecular formula $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{66}\text{O}_{14}$. Of the 42 carbon signals in its ^{13}C nmr spectrum, 12 signals between δ 62.0 and 107.0 demonstrated

Fig 1 NOE interactions (\leftrightarrow) and HMBC correlations (\dashrightarrow) of 3 and 5

the presence of two sugar units in the molecule. The appearance of a singlet at δ 199.96 indicated the presence of an α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group in the molecule supported by the uv-maximum at 248 nm. A comparison of the ^{13}C nmr spectrum of 4 with that of 2 (Table 1) revealed that the two compounds differ with respect to the substitution pattern in C/D ring system of the aglycone moiety. Thus, the deshielding of C-9, C-12 and C-13 of 4 by \sim 14.0, 5.5, and 24.0 ppm clearly indicated the location of the carbonyl group at C-11. This contention was further supported by the appearance of the vinylic proton (H-12) signal as a sharp singlet at a lower field (δ 5.961) in contrast to the triplet at

TABLE 3—ONE-BOND (^1H - ^{13}C COSY) AND MULTIPLE-BOND (HMBC) ^1H - ^{13}C CORRELATION DATA OF THE AGLYCONE MOIETY OF 4

δ_{H} ppm	One-bond correlation δ_{C} ppm	Multiple-bond correlation δ_{C} ppm			
1.337 (H ₃ -23)	28.26 (C-23)	17.05 (C-24)	39.93 (C-4)	55.46 (C-5)	88.63 (C-3)
1.033 (H ₃ -24)	17.05 (C-24)	28.26 (C-23)	39.93 (C-4)	55.46 (C-5)	88.63 (C-3)
1.240 (H ₃ -25)	16.73 (C-25)	37.48 (C-1)	37.48 (C-10)	55.46 (C-5)	62.17 (C-9)
1.279 (H ₃ -26)	19.48 (C-26)	33.19 (C-7)	44.00 (C-8)	46.51 (C-14)	62.17 (C-9)
1.430 (H ₃ -27)	23.65 (C-27)	28.19 (C-15)	44.00 (C-8)	46.51 (C-14)	168.79 (C-13)
0.903 (H ₃ -29)	32.80 (C-29)	23.34 (C-30)	30.69 (C-20)	33.77 (C-21)	44.32 (C-19)
0.808 (H ₃ -30)	23.34 (C-30)	30.69 (C-20)	32.80 (C-29)	33.77 (C-21)	44.32 (C-19)

δ 5.446 (J 3.4 Hz) in the spectrum of **2**. Some other ^{13}C signals, particularly for C-14 and C-26 were also deshielded by ~ 4 and 2 ppm respectively, presumably due to the change in the ring C conformation consequent upon the introduction of the carbonyl group at C-11. The assigned structure of the aglycone was further corroborated by the 2D-HMBC data (Table 3). Moreover, the ^{13}C chemical shifts of C-3 and C-28 of the aglycone moiety as well as those of the two sugar units were found to be very close to those of **2** (Table 1) demonstrating that two D-glucose units are attached to C-3 and C-28 of the 11-oxo-oleanolic acid.

Based on the above observations, elateroside A could be represented by 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3 β -hydroxy-11-oxo-olean-12-en-28-oic acid 28-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside structure (**4**).

Compound **5**, designated as elateroside B, m.p. 232–34°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} + 7.1^\circ$, showed in its negative ion FAB-MS, the $[\text{M-H}]^-$ at m/z 941 corresponding to the molecular formula $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{78}\text{O}_{18}$. The spectrum also exhibited fragment ions at m/z 779 ($[\text{M-H}]^- - 162$), 617 ($[\text{M-H}]^- - 162 \times 2$), and 455 ($[\text{M-H}]^- - 162 \times 3$) due to successive loss of three hexose sugar units from $[\text{M-H}]^-$. Its ^{13}C nmr spectrum displayed signals for 48 carbons, of which 18 belong to three sugar units and 30 to the triterpenoid aglycone moiety. Two- and three-bond correlations of the methyl protons with the neighbouring carbons of the aglycone in the HMBC spectrum (Table 4) clearly revealed that the aglycone is oleanolic

acid and a trisaccharide moiety is attached to C-3 of oleanolic acid. As expected, ^{13}C chemical shifts of the aglycone carbons of **5** were very close to those of **1-3** (Table 1). The monosaccharide units of the trisaccharide moiety were identified as D-glucose and D-galactose (2 : 1) by acid-hydrolysis followed by HPTLC of the formed monosaccharides, as well as by GC of their alditol acetates. The three anomeric proton signals at δ 4.840, 5.297, and 5.687 as doublets with J 7.6–7.9 Hz indicated that the monosaccharide units are β -linked.

The chemical shifts of individual protons of two glucose units could be ascertained from a combination of 2D ^1H - ^1H HOHAHA and ^1H - ^1H COSY spectral analyses. Thus, the following vicinal ^1H - ^1H correlations for two glucose residues were obtained :

- (i) 4.840 (G-H-1) \leftrightarrow 4.36 (G-H-2) \leftrightarrow 4.25 (G-H-3) \leftrightarrow 4.04 (G-H-4) \leftrightarrow 3.84 (G-H-5) \leftrightarrow 4.48 (G-H-6)
- (ii) 5.687 (G'-H-1) \leftrightarrow 4.10 (G'-H-2) \leftrightarrow 4.27 (G'-H-3) \leftrightarrow 4.17 (G'-H-4) \leftrightarrow 3.84 (G'-H-5) \leftrightarrow 4.33 and 4.47 (G'-H-6)

For galactose moiety, correlations for only H-1, H-2, and H-3 could be established. However, ^1H chemical shifts for H-4, H-5, and H-6 could be determined from the correlations of the remaining three ^{13}C signals in the ^1H - ^{13}C COSY spectrum.

TABLE 4—ONE-BOND (^1H - ^{13}C COSY) AND MULTIPLE-BOND (HMBC) ^1H - ^{13}C CORRELATION DATA OF **5**

δ_{H} ppm	One-bond correlation	Multiple-bond correlation			
	δ_{C} ppm	δ_{C} ppm			
1.271 (H ₃ -23)	28.02 (C-23)	16.76 (C-24)	39.60 (C-4)	55.77 (C-5)	89.33 (C-3)
1.082 (H ₃ -24)	16.76 (C-24)	28.02 (C-23)	39.60 (C-4)	55.77 (C-5)	89.33 (C-3)
0.791 (H ₃ -25)	15.44 (C-25)	36.95 (C-10)	38.67 (C-1)	47.97 (C-9)	55.77 (C-5)
0.980 (H ₃ -26)	17.40 (C-26)	39.72 (C-8)	42.16 (C-14)	47.97 (C-9)	
1.306 (H ₃ -27)	26.21 (C-27)	28.33 (C-15)	39.72 (C-8)	42.16 (C-14)	144.90 (C-13)
0.964 (H ₃ -29)	33.31 (C-29)	23.79 (C-30)	30.99 (C-20)	34.25 (C-21)	46.52 (C-19)
1.021 (H ₃ -30)	23.79 (C-30)	30.99 (C-20)	33.31 (C-29)	34.25 (C-21)	46.52 (C-19)
3.31 (H-18)	42.03 (C-18)	46.69 (C-17)	122.51 (C-12)	144.90 (C-13)	
3.285 (H-3)	89.33 (C-3)	104.99 (G-C-1)			
5.477 (H-12)	122.51 (C-12)	23.72 (C-11)	42.16 (C-14)	47.97 (C-9)	
4.840 (G-H-1)	104.99 (G-C-1)	89.33 (C-3)			
5.297 (Gal-H-1)	105.24 (Gal-C-1)	88.71 (G-C-3)			
5.687 (G'-H-1)	103.82 (G'-C-1)	79.28 (G-C-2)			
4.25 (G-H-3)	88.71 (G-C-3)	69.98 (G-C-4)	79.28 (G-C-2)	105.24 (Gal-C-1)	
4.04 (G-H-4)	69.98 (G-C-4)	62.60 (G-C-6)	77.66 (G-C-5)	88.71 (G-C-3)	

Having thus assigned all the ^{13}C and ^1H nmr chemical shifts of the sugar units (Tables 1 and 2), it is clear that the galactose and one glucose units are linked to C-2 and C-3 of another glucose unit which is attached to C-3 of the aglycone. The exact position of attachment of the terminal galactose and glucose units to the inner glucose could be derived as follows.

HMBC correlations (Table 4) between (i) galactose anomeric proton (Gal-H-1) and C-3 of inner glucose (G-C-3), (ii) terminal glucose anomeric proton (G'-H-1) and C-2 of inner glucose (G-C-2), and (iii) anomeric proton of the inner glucose (G-H-1) and C-3 of oleanolic acid established that galactose and glucose units are attached respectively to C-3 and C-2 of the inner glucose unit. In total agreement with the above contention, the NOESY spectrum of the compound exhibited, among others, NOE interactions (Fig. 1) between (i) Gal-H-1 and G-H-3, (ii) G'-H-1 and G-H-2, and (iii) G-H-1 and H-3 of the aglycone. The proximity of the H-4 and H₂-6 of the terminal glucose to H-1 of the terminal galactose, as evidenced from the observed NOE interactions (Fig. 1), was also in excellent agreement with the proposed structure.

Thus, elateroside B could be represented as oleanolic acid 3-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3) [β -D-glucopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 2)]- β -D-glucopyranoside (5).

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. NMR: JEOL ALPHA 500 (500 MHz for ^1H , 125 MHz for ^{13}C) with TMS as int. standard; FAB-MS: JEOL HX-110 with glycerol as the matrix; HPLC: SENSU PAK C₁₈ column (8 mm \times 250 mm, 5 μm), MeOH-H₂O (4 : 1) as mobile phase and detector RI; GC: Hewlett-Packard 5730A, ECNSS-M (3% Gas Chrome Q) at 190° for alditol acetates; HPTLC: precoated Si gel plates (E. Merck) were used.

Fresh fruits of *E. elaterium* were collected from local market in Calcutta in July, 1995.

Fresh fruits (10 kg) were cut into small thin pieces and extracted with MeOH at room temperature. The extract was concentrated and fatty materials were removed by petroleum ether extraction. The aq. part was then shaken with CHCl₃ when the entire turbid material present in the aq. solution migrated into the CHCl₃ layer leaving the aq. layer clear. The CHCl₃ layer was evaporated to a gummy residue (5 g) which was chromatographed over silica gel (100 g) using CHCl₃ and CHCl₃-MeOH mixture with increasing proportion of MeOH to get three fractions. Each fraction was further purified by repeated chromatography over silica gel and final purification was done by prep.-HPLC to obtain 1 (50 mg), 2 (20 mg), 3 (30 mg), 4 (3 mg), and 5 (20 mg).

Oleanolic acid 3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (1): It was crystallised from MeOH as shining colourless cubes, m.p. 235–36° (lit.⁶ 225–29°), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 54.3^\circ$ (c 0.4, MeOH) (lit.⁶ +46.9°); FAB-MS (negative) m/z 617 [M-H]⁻; ^{13}C nmr: Table 1; ^1H nmr: Table 2.

3-O- β -D-Glucopyranosyl-3 β -hydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid 28-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (2): It had m.p. 168–70°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 18.5^\circ$ (c 0.3, MeOH), FAB-MS (positive) m/z 803 [M + Na]⁺; ^{13}C nmr: Table 1; ^1H nmr: 0.854, 0.896, 0.922, 1.011, 1.112, 1.278 and 1.323 (3H each, s, 7 \times Me), 3.394 (1H, dd, J 11.7, 4.4 Hz, H-3), 4.951 (1H, d, J 7.9 Hz, G-H-1), 5.446 (1H, t, J 3.4 Hz, H-12) and 6.343 (1H, d, J 7.9 Hz, G'-H-1).

Oleanolic acid 3-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 2)- β -D-glucopyranoside (3): It was crystallised from MeOH as white powder, m.p. 201–02°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} - 24.6^\circ$ (c 0.2, MeOH) (lit.⁸ m.p. 265–70°d, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 36.5^\circ$); FAB-MS (negative) m/z 779 [M-H]⁻, 617 ([M-H]⁻-162), 455 ([M-H]⁻-162 \times 2); ^{13}C nmr: Table 1; ^1H nmr: Table 2.

Elateroside A (4): It had m.p. 158–60°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 15.2^\circ$ (c 0.3, MeOH); FAB-MS (negative) m/z 793 [M-H]⁻; ^{13}C nmr: Table 1; ^1H nmr: Table 2.

Elateroside B (5): It was crystallised from MeOH-MeCN as colourless needles, m.p. 232–34°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 7.1^\circ$ (c 1.2, MeOH); FAB-MS (negative) m/z 941 ([M-H]⁻, 779 ([M-H]⁻-162), 617 ([M-H]⁻-162 \times 2), 455 ([M-H]⁻-162 \times 3); ^{13}C nmr Table 1; ^1H nmr: Table 2.

Hydrolysis of 1, 3, and 5: Compounds 1, 3, and 5 (5 mg each) were separately hydrolysed with 1 N HCl in dioxane-H₂O (1 : 1; 1 ml) on a steam-bath for 1 h. Dioxane was then removed from the reaction mixtures in a rotary evaporator and the concentrated solutions were diluted with H₂O (0.5 ml) and extracted with EtOAc. The residues of the EtOAc extracts were identified as oleanolic acid by direct comparison (^1H nmr) with an authentic specimen. The monosaccharide constituents present in the aq. solutions were identified as D-glucose in case of 1 and 3, and D-glucose and D-galactose in ratio 2 : 1 in case of 5 by HPTLC as well as by comparison of the gas chromatogram of their alditol acetates with those of authentic specimens.

Hydrolysis of 2: Compound 2 (5 mg) was hydrolysed with 5% aqueous methanolic NaOH (2 ml) on a steam-bath for 2 h. Most of the solvent was then removed from the reaction mixture in a rotary evaporator, the syrupy residue was diluted with water (2 ml), and extracted with EtOAc (3 \times 5 ml). The residue of the EtOAc extract was identified as 1 (^1H nmr). The aqueous solution was acidified with dilute HCl and concentrated in a rotary evaporator. PC of the concentrate showed the presence of D-glucose.

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